

Beyond Post-Hoc: A SHAP-Based Feature Selection Framework for High-Accuracy, Class-Aware Intrusion Detection

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Abstract—Explainable AI (XAI) has gained prominence in Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) to address the opacity of black-box models. However, existing efforts have largely confined XAI to post-hoc interpretability, with limited exploration of its potential for driving data refinement and model optimisation. To the best of our knowledge, SHAPRefine is the first model-agnostic feature selection framework that systematically integrates class-wise SHAP value aggregation with automated refinement to produce lightweight and high-performing IDS models. Unlike existing SHAP-based methods that repeatedly recompute Shapley values for each candidate subset—often requiring excessive retraining and parameter tuning—SHAPRefine introduces a performance-driven iterative selection strategy that minimizes redundant computations while explicitly accounting for minority-class contributions. Comprehensive evaluations across diverse IDS datasets and classifiers demonstrate that SHAPRefine consistently reduces feature dimensionality by up to 90%, cuts training time and energy consumption, and improves detection accuracy across all attack types, with F1-score gains of up to 95% for minority classes. These results establish SHAPRefine as a robust and resource-efficient solution for accurate IDS deployment in Beyond 5G (B5G) and 6G networks.

Index Terms—Intrusion detection system, Explainable AI, SHAP, Feature selection, Multiclass classification, 5G/6G

I. INTRODUCTION

Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) are critical for safeguarding modern networks, yet the growing scale, heterogeneity, and complexity of traffic in Beyond 5G (B5G) environments demand detection mechanisms that are both accurate and efficient. Machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) have shown strong potential for intrusion detection but are often criticised for their “black-box” nature, where decision-making remains opaque. Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) techniques such as LIME [1] and SHAP [2] have addressed this by providing interpretable insights into model behaviour, enabling model debugging, trust-building, and post-hoc analysis.

However, most IDS research has applied XAI only for interpretability after model training, with little impact on improving the model itself. Many studies have utilized XAI’s top-ranked features to perform simple feature selection [3],

[4]; however, these approaches are often manual, yield only marginal detection gains, and tend to be dependent on the specific dataset, model, or attack class. More advanced SHAP-based refinement techniques have recently been proposed [5], [6], but they remain constrained by model dependency, scalability challenges on large datasets, and limited validation in multiclass intrusion scenarios. Moreover, the system-level implications of XAI-driven methods, such as efficiency, scalability, and computational cost, are rarely considered. Thus, there remains a clear gap in IDS research that goes beyond utilizing XAI in its traditional scope of interpretability. This work addresses this gap by using XAI explanations to systematically refine models for higher detection performance, improved efficiency, and robustness.

We introduce **SHAPRefine**, a model-agnostic feature selection framework that leverages class-wise SHAP value aggregation to drive systematic feature reduction while explicitly addressing class imbalance in IDS datasets. Experimental results demonstrate that SHAPRefine consistently improves overall detection accuracy and class-specific F1-scores, with substantial gains for minority classes. By reducing feature dimensionality, execution time, CPU load, and energy consumption by up to 90%, SHAPRefine enables efficient and practical IDS deployment in next-generation network environments. The major contributions of this work are as follows:

- **XAI-Driven IDS Refinement:** While prior works have been restricted to post-hoc interpretability, *SHAPRefine is the very first framework* to transform SHAP explanations into an automated, class-aware feature selection mechanism that directly enhances IDS detection accuracy.
- **Minority-Class Awareness:** To improve representation of minority attacks and mitigate bias toward majority classes, SHAPRefine introduces a novel class-balanced aggregation strategy that preserves discriminative signals from minority intrusions in imbalanced IDS datasets.
- **Generality Across Models and Datasets:** SHAPRefine advances the field by demonstrating scalability across heterogeneous classifier families (XGBoost, Deep Neural Networks, Logistic Regression) and four benchmark IDS datasets, including modern 5G traffic scenarios.
- **Computational Efficiency:** Unlike works that neglect

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system-level considerations, SHAPRefine explicitly incorporates efficiency metrics into its evaluation. By eliminating repeated SHAP recomputations and employing a performance-driven iterative refinement process, SHAPRefine achieves substantially lower computational costs while improving accuracy, thereby enabling efficient and robust IDS deployment in B5G environments.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews existing literature on feature selection in the context of IDS. Section III introduces the proposed SHAPRefine framework. Section IV outlines the implementation details. Results will then be discussed in Section V. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper and outlines future research directions.

II. RELATED WORKS

A. Feature Selection for Intrusion Detection

Feature selection is an important step in IDS design, as it reduces dimensionality, eliminates redundancy, and improves generalization to unseen traffic [7], [8]. Prior studies show that training models on reduced feature sets can yield faster convergence and better accuracy without sacrificing detection performance [9]. To improve performance further, researchers have explored various hybrid methods. For example, [10] introduced a two-phase IDS using a multi-parent mutation wrapper with a Support Vector Machine (SVM) and an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) optimized by gravitational search and PSO, achieving 99.3% accuracy on NSL-KDD. Other studies, such as [11], combined correlation-based selection with k-means clustering and Sequential Minimal Optimization (SMO), while [12] proposed a density-aware k-means algorithm enhanced with Kd-tree pruning and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for faster convergence and improved detection. However, these approaches often achieve performance gains at the cost of computational efficiency due to their reliance on multi-stage pipelines, which can be prohibitively slow and resource-heavy.

B. XAI for Feature Reduction

Recent studies have moved beyond post-hoc interpretability by leveraging XAI for proactive feature selection in IDS. For example, the SPIP framework [4] combined SHAP, PFI, ICE, and PDP to identify relevant features for Long short-term memory (LSTM) models. Similarly, the Xplique-based framework [13] applied nine XAI methods to score and rank features through a voting system. Although promising, these approaches achieved only marginal gains and introduced significant computational overhead due to reliance on multiple attribution techniques.

Beyond these, strategic SHAP-driven feature selection frameworks have emerged, including BorutaSHAP [14], PowerSHAP [5], and IterSHAP [6]. BorutaSHAP extends the Boruta algorithm using Shapley values and shadow features, but is constrained to tree-based models and requires repeated SHAP computations for each feature–shadow comparison, increasing runtime on large datasets. PowerSHAP introduces a statistical hypothesis test to retain features outperforming a

TABLE I: Comparison of feature selection methods for IDS

Method	Model-Agnostic	Automated Configuration	Multiclass Application	Scalability	IDS Dataset Diversity
Hybrid SVM+ANN [10]	X	X	✓	X	X
Correlation+KMeans+SMO [11]	X	X	✓	X	X
Density-aware KMeans+PCA [12]	X	X	✓	X	X
BorutaSHAP [14]	X	X	X	X	X
IterSHAP [6]	✓	X	X	X	X
PowerSHAP [5]	✓	✓	X	X	X
SHAPRefine	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

random baseline, but the method requires re-training the model for every candidate subset, which scales poorly with high-dimensional feature spaces. IterSHAP selects feature subsets iteratively by training and evaluating a model at each step until a lower limit is reached, but this involves manual parameter tuning for each dataset and no built-in optimisation to reduce repeated computations.

Table I summarizes feature selection methods proposed in the literature. While several approaches support multiclass application, they are constrained by algorithm-specific designs, lack automation, and show limited scalability across diverse IDS datasets. In contrast, SHAPRefine uniquely combines model-agnostic capabilities, automated configuration, scalability across classifiers and datasets, and class-aware refinement.

III. METHODOLOGY

Fig. 1 illustrates the proposed SHAPRefine framework for enhancing the efficiency and predictive performance of intrusion detection systems. This framework is model-agnostic and can be applied to any multiclass model due to SHAP’s scalability and flexibility across diverse model structures. Upon data preprocessing and initial model training, SHAPRefine algorithm will be deployed, consisting of four main steps: (i) SHAP value computation, (ii) class-wise normalization and weighting, (iii) global feature importance aggregation, and (iv) an iterative selection process that incrementally builds an optimal feature subset guided by the aggregated scores. In the final Model Evaluation stage, the IDS model is retrained using the refined feature subset and evaluated on a held-out test set. This enables a direct comparison with the baseline model in terms of both overall and per-class prediction performance. The implementation details of the feature aggregation and selection procedures are provided in Algorithms 1 and 2.

Fig. 1: Overview of the SHAPRefine framework.

A. SHAP Values Computation

We first compute Shapley values on the training data to quantify each feature’s contribution to class predictions. Grounded in cooperative game theory, Shapley values capture the marginal effect of a feature across all possible coalitions [2]. Values may be positive or negative, indicating whether a feature increases or decreases the predicted probability of a given class.

In our approach, we emphasize positive contributions, as they highlight the features that drive predictions towards specific attack classes. This is particularly critical for under-represented classes, where identifying discriminative signals is essential. Formally, for each class $c \in \{1, \dots, C\}$ and feature f , we compute the average positive contribution as:

$$P_c[f] = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \max(0, \text{SHAP}_{i,f}^{(c)}) \quad (1)$$

where n is the total number of training instances, and $\text{SHAP}_{i,f}^{(c)}$ is the SHAP value for instance i , feature f , and class c .

B. Class-Wise Normalization & Weighting

Since SHAP magnitudes vary across classes, direct aggregation risks biasing towards majority classes. To address this, each class-wise SHAP vector is normalized using min–max scaling:

$$\hat{P}_c[f] = \frac{P_c[f] - \min(P_c)}{\max(P_c) - \min(P_c)} \quad (2)$$

We then assign a weight w_c to each class c based on its inverse frequency in the training set:

$$w_c = \frac{1}{\text{freq}(c)} \quad (3)$$

C. Global Feature Importance Aggregation

The overall importance score for each feature is calculated as the weighted average of its normalized class-wise scores:

$$S[f] = \frac{1}{\sum_c w_c} \sum_{c=1}^C w_c \cdot \hat{P}_c[f] \quad (4)$$

This formulation balances global and class-specific relevance, ensuring that minority-class features are preserved in the ranking rather than being overshadowed by majority-class signals.

D. Iterative Feature Selection

Once features are ranked by their aggregated SHAP importance scores $S[f]$, we extract an optimal subset via a performance-driven refinement strategy. Starting with an empty set, we iteratively test the inclusion of the next highest-ranked feature from $S[f]$. At each step, the model is retrained and its performance is evaluated using k -fold cross-validation. A feature is added only if its inclusion yields a measurable improvement in validation performance. This ensures that the

model is not just accumulating features, but is building a subset where features work together to enhance predictive accuracy. The process terminates when no further performance gain is observed, indicating that the model has reached its optimal feature configuration. By dynamically adapting to the dataset and model behavior, this selection mechanism prevents the inclusion of redundant or noisy features that might be highly ranked but offer no benefit when combined with others.

Algorithm 1 SHAP Value Aggregation with Class Normalization and Weighting

Input: Training data $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$, baseline model M
Output: Overall feature importance scores $S[f]$

- 1: Compute $\text{SHAP}_{i,f}^{(c)}$ for all i, f, c using M on $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$
- 2: **for** class $c = 1$ to C **do**
- 3: **for** feature f **do**
- 4: $P_c[f] \leftarrow \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \max(0, \text{SHAP}_{i,f}^{(c)})$
- 5: **end for**
- 6: Normalize: $\hat{P}_c[f] \leftarrow \frac{P_c[f] - \min(P_c)}{\max(P_c) - \min(P_c)}$
- 7: Weight: $w_c \leftarrow \frac{1}{\text{freq}(c)}$
- 8: **end for**
- 9: **for** feature f **do**
- 10: $S[f] \leftarrow \frac{1}{\sum_c w_c} \sum_{c=1}^C w_c \cdot \hat{P}_c[f]$
- 11: **end for**
- 12: **return** $S[f]$

Algorithm 2 Iterative Feature Subset Refinement

Input: Aggregated feature scores $S[f]$, training data $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}}$, model N
Output: Optimal feature subset \mathcal{F}_{opt}

- 1: Sort features by $S[f]$ (descending)
- 2: Initialize $\mathcal{F}_{\text{opt}} \leftarrow \emptyset$
- 3: Initialize $\text{CV}_{\text{opt}} \leftarrow$ baseline CV performance
- 4: **for** f in $S[f]$ **do**
- 5: $\mathcal{F}_{\text{tmp}} \leftarrow \mathcal{F}_{\text{opt}} \cup \{f\}$
- 6: Train N on \mathcal{F}_{tmp}
- 7: Evaluate via k -fold cross-validation
- 8: **if** $\text{CV}_{\text{tmp}} > \text{CV}_{\text{opt}}$ **then**
- 9: $\mathcal{F}_{\text{opt}} \leftarrow \mathcal{F}_{\text{tmp}}$
- 10: $\text{CV}_{\text{opt}} \leftarrow \text{CV}_{\text{tmp}}$
- 11: **end if**
- 12: **end for**
- 13: **return** \mathcal{F}_{opt}

IV. EXPERIMENTAL IMPLEMENTATION

A. Dataset Preprocessing

To evaluate the robustness and generalizability of our proposed framework, we selected four widely recognized IDS benchmark datasets. These datasets were chosen to represent a diverse range of network environments, traffic types, and attack scenarios, from traditional enterprise networks to modern 5G infrastructures.

UNSW-NB15: This dataset [15] contains over 2.5 million records and covers nine distinct attack categories: Fuzzers, Analysis, Backdoors, DoS, Exploits, Generic, Reconnaissance, Shellcode, and Worms.

NSL-KDD: A refined version of the KDD’99 dataset [16], it contains 125,973 training and 22,544 testing instances across four primary attack types: Denial of Service (DoS), Probe, Remote-to-Local (R2L), and User-to-Root (U2R).

5G-NIDD: Generated from a real 5G wireless network [17], this dataset includes traffic from various attack scenarios, such as DoS (ICMP, UDP, SYN, HTTP Floods) and multiple types of port scans.

NetsLab-5GORAN-IDD: Collected from a physical 5G Open RAN testbed [18], this multi-modal dataset contains network- and radio-level metrics for attacks including DoS, DDoS, Probe, Brute Force, and Web Attacks.

For all datasets, categorical features, such as protocol and service attributes, were one-hot encoded, and all continuous features were normalized using min-max scaling to prevent features with large ranges from disproportionately influencing model training. Datasets with detailed attack subcategories were consolidated into their broader parent attack classes.

B. Model Configuration

To evaluate the model-agnostic capabilities of our framework, we selected three baseline models spanning distinct algorithmic families. XGBoost was chosen as a representative tree-based ensemble model, well-suited for heterogeneous tabular data and capable of capturing complex non-linear feature interactions. A DNN was included as a representative DL architecture, offering the ability to learn hierarchical feature representations that can uncover subtle intrusion patterns. Logistic Regression was selected as a classical linear model, providing a simple yet interpretable baseline for assessing the effect of feature selection on models with limited representational capacity. To ensure fair and consistent evaluation across all datasets, we employed a fixed set of hyperparameters for each model, as detailed in Table II. This design isolates the contribution of SHAPRefine’s feature selection process, rather than conflating results with dataset-specific hyperparameter optimization, while still reflecting standard and robust baseline configurations for each model.

C. Evaluation Metrics

Predictive performance is evaluated using accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, as these collectively capture both overall and class-wise effectiveness. We also assess model efficiency using system-level metrics that quantify resource consumption during model training and testing. Specifically, we measure execution time to capture latency, average CPU computational effort—defined as the product of mean CPU utilization and execution time—to reflect processing intensity, and average memory usage to estimate memory footprint. Additionally, we estimate energy consumption to account for environmental sustainability.

D. Statistical Analysis

To assess the statistical significance of performance differences between models trained on full and SHAP-selected feature sets, we applied 10-fold stratified cross-validation to generate paired scores. These scores were compared using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, chosen for its non-parametric nature and robustness without normality assumptions.

TABLE II: Hyperparameter Configuration for Baseline Models

Model	Hyperparameters & Architecture
XGBoost	n_estimators=200, max_depth=5, learning_rate=0.1, objective='multi:softprob'
Logistic Regression	penalty='l2', solver='lbfgs', max_iter=1000, multi_class='multinomial'
DNN	Two hidden layers (128, 64) with ReLU activation & 0.3 Dropout; Softmax output; Adam optimizer with learning_rate=0.001; loss='sparse_categorical_crossentropy'.

E. Development platform and tools

The proposed system was implemented in Python 3.10.12 and evaluated on a machine with an Intel Core Ultra 7 165U processor and 64 GB RAM. To collect efficiency metrics, we instrumented the evaluation pipeline with fine-grained profiling using a suite of Python packages: *psutil*¹ for CPU utilization, *memory_profiler*² for memory footprint, and *CodeCarbon*³ to estimate energy consumption. All measurements are computed exclusively over the execution of training and inference routines, isolating them from background processes and overall device activity.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Prediction Performance Comparison with Baseline Models

Table III presents a comparative evaluation of baseline models trained on the full feature set versus those utilising SHAPRefine-selected features, including the corresponding p-values from paired statistical tests. Across all datasets, SHAPRefine consistently enhances predictive performance, suggesting that the original datasets contain redundant or irrelevant features that introduce noise and limit the generalization capability of baseline models. The most pronounced gains are observed on UNSW-NB15, where XGBoost achieves a 10% accuracy increase and a 16% gain in F1-score. These improvements are statistically significant across all metrics, demonstrating the efficacy of SHAPRefine’s feature reduction. Similar but smaller gains are observed on the 5GORAN-IDD and 5G-NIDD datasets, where recall and F1 improvements remain statistically significant, underscoring SHAPRefine’s ability to improve calibration and reduce overfitting even in cleaner data regimes. Beyond overall performance, SHAPRefine substantially improves minority-class detection. On NSL-KDD, XGBoost’s F1-score for R2L attacks rises from 12.6% to 51.2%, and for U2R from 13.2% to 60.1%, while Worm detection on UNSW-NB15 improves from 22.2% to 72.5%.

B. Efficiency Performance Comparison with Baseline Models

Table IV reports system-level metrics when training and deploying models on the SHAPRefine-selected subsets compared to the full feature sets. A consistent trend emerges across datasets: dimensionality is reduced by over 80–90%, directly translating into faster training and lower computational

¹<https://github.com/giampaolo/psutil>

²https://github.com/python-memory-profiler/memory_profiler

³<https://mlco2.github.io/codecarbon/>

TABLE III: Predictive performance of baseline models trained on the full feature set versus the SHAPRefine-selected subset.

Dataset	Model	Overall Model Performance				Individual Class F1-Scores												
		Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Benign	DoS	Probe/PortScan	Exploits	Generic	Worms	R2L	U2R	DDoS	BruteForce	Web	Bot	Infiltration
UNSW-NB15	XGBoost (Baseline)	68.74	63.39	57.23	57.65	85.19	28.34	67.30	71.24	71.61	22.22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	XGBoost (SHAPRefine)	79.39†	74.04†	75.28†	73.92†	85.58	40.41	74.01	72.36	98.63	72.53	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Log Reg (Baseline)	57.59	44.81	45.12	42.93	72.41	34.52	38.81	51.86	59.97	11.37	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Log Reg (SHAPRefine)	72.22†	53.86†	56.38†	53.42†	75.46	40.28	49.49	62.22	93.06	58.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	DNN (Baseline)	61.50	54.69	48.23	47.53	77.16	23.54	55.17	64.33	64.95	16.10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	DNN (SHAPRefine)	76.69†	59.80†	60.17	58.68†	85.32	37.26	71.62	68.32	97.58	68.09	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NSL-KDD	XGBoost (Baseline)	77.17	79.46	51.69	53.29	79.61	89.40	71.70	-	-	12.56	13.16	-	-	-	-	-	-
	XGBoost (SHAPRefine)	82.55†	87.46†	68.59†	69.71†	82.82	92.28	85.63	-	-	51.17	60.09	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Log Reg (Baseline)	76.19	74.05	57.40	59.73	77.90	88.07	78.01	-	-	7.74	46.94	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Log Reg (SHAPRefine)	80.94†	76.25†	62.60†	62.59†	80.94	88.77	83.42	-	-	39.31	51.51	-	-	-	-	-	-
	DNN (Baseline)	77.28	84.59	57.17	60.43	86.13	79.31	82.66	-	-	18.10	35.96	-	-	-	-	-	-
	DNN (SHAPRefine)	78.34†	82.93†	57.99†	60.66†	80.84	89.71	75.54	-	-	15.84	41.38	-	-	-	-	-	-
5GORAN-IDD	XGBoost (Baseline)	92.37	84.50	82.01	83.08	99.91	91.34	94.10	-	-	-	-	-	87.54	26.20	99.30	-	-
	XGBoost (SHAPRefine)	94.79†	87.12†	86.86†	86.91†	100.00	94.98	95.37	-	-	-	-	-	89.91	43.71	99.48	-	-
	Log Reg (Baseline)	82.84	87.28	66.51	67.22	98.98	80.50	35.85	-	-	-	-	-	85.26	2.27	99.42	-	-
	Log Reg (SHAPRefine)	84.97†	90.49†	68.81†	70.34†	100.00	86.31	39.60	-	-	-	-	-	87.43	26.02	99.64	-	-
	DNN (Baseline)	94.65	89.06	86.41	87.09	99.78	90.18	89.51	-	-	-	-	-	90.57	51.62	99.42	-	-
	DNN (SHAPRefine)	95.22	90.86†	87.42	87.54†	100.00	93.83	89.45	-	-	-	-	-	90.88	50.75	99.43	-	-
5G-NIDD	XGBoost (Baseline)	97.02	96.19	97.13	96.65	96.50	97.47	95.99	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	XGBoost (SHAPRefine)	98.68†	99.19†	98.91	99.04	98.83	98.30	100.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Log Reg (Baseline)	95.19	95.77	96.18	95.97	95.08	96.43	96.41	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Log Reg (SHAPRefine)	96.29†	96.71†	97.16†	96.93†	95.40	96.72	98.66	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	DNN (Baseline)	96.50	96.68	88.63	96.13	95.81	96.33	93.25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	DNN (SHAPRefine)	98.38	99.02†	98.61†	98.80†	97.93	98.57	99.90	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Symbols denote statistical significance relative to the baseline model: † $p < 0.05$. No symbol indicates non-significance.

TABLE IV: Efficiency performance of baseline models trained on the full feature set versus the SHAPRefine-selected subset.

Dataset	Model	Number of Features	Training Time (s)	Inference Time (s)	CPU Effort (%)	Average Memory Usage (MB)	Energy Consumed (mWh)
UNSW-NB15	XGBoost (Baseline)	194	566.17	0.85	1842.32	1727.79	5704.06
	XGBoost (SHAPRefine)	9	43.11	0.73	143.03	1244.26	442.03
	Log Reg (Baseline)	194	77.17	0.32	7697.70	1712.67	779.76
	Log Reg (SHAPRefine)	19	22.41	0.14	2242.22	1266.82	227.40
	DNN (Baseline)	194	443.84	205.62	2135.76	2434.39	6525.41
	DNN (SHAPRefine)	11	18.00	6.43	90.24	1475.01	246.27
NSL-KDD	XGBoost (Baseline)	122	183.20	0.26	1141.84	961.18	1846.26
	XGBoost (SHAPRefine)	23	47.89	0.24	385.76	740.84	484.48
	Log Reg (Baseline)	122	39.81	0.13	3965.12	923.50	402.18
	Log Reg (SHAPRefine)	15	9.85	0.12	982.73	726.26	101.18
	DNN (Baseline)	122	56.06	9.43	309.37	1098.00	658.85
	DNN (SHAPRefine)	21	21.30	3.34	134.18	903.60	248.27
5GORAN-IDD	XGBoost (Baseline)	62	1151.73	2.71	3958.26	2641.66	11613.41
	XGBoost (SHAPRefine)	9	306.78	2.47	1090.45	1639.91	3111.72
	Log Reg (Baseline)	62	321.01	0.35	16741.15	2556.78	3232.79
	Log Reg (SHAPRefine)	14	174.28	0.19	10362.24	1715.46	1755.95
	DNN (Baseline)	62	231.56	47.98	1078.42	4211.08	2809.53
	DNN (SHAPRefine)	10	77.98	11.02	389.76	2232.41	895.66
5G-NIDD	XGBoost (Baseline)	57	518.91	1.10	1935.32	2324.52	5231.07
	XGBoost (SHAPRefine)	11	165.63	1.02	601.64	1655.37	1676.41
	Log Reg (Baseline)	57	205.74	0.28	14484.10	2273.12	2072.77
	Log Reg (SHAPRefine)	12	50.62	0.15	4580.14	1662.43	510.88
	DNN (Baseline)	57	337.05	76.25	1537.05	3351.81	4153.20
	DNN (SHAPRefine)	11	109.76	21.76	512.52	2182.44	1322.76

load. For instance, in UNSW-NB15 the feature space shrinks from 194 to fewer than 20 attributes, with XGBoost training time falling from 566.2s to 43.1s and DNN training time from 443.8s to 18.0s. Similar patterns appear across the datasets, where both inference latency and training time are substantially reduced. The reduction in input dimensionality also yields pronounced savings in CPU effort, memory usage, and energy consumption. DNNs in particular show 60–90% lower resource demands, reflecting fewer parameters in early layers and faster convergence. Importantly, these efficiency gains persist in settings where predictive accuracy is already high, such as 5G-NIDD, highlighting that feature refinement optimizes system cost without jeopardizing accuracy gains.

C. Performance Comparison with Feature Selection Methods

To validate the effectiveness of SHAPRefine, we compared it against established feature selection (FS) techniques, in-

cluding Mutual Information (MI), Recursive Feature Elimination with cross-validation (RFECV), BorutaSHAP, and PowerSHAP, using XGBoost on the 5G-NIDD dataset. For fairness, the number of features selected by MI was matched to SHAPRefine’s, enabling a direct comparison under similar dimensionality constraints. Table V reports both predictive and efficiency results, where the efficiency metrics correspond solely to the FS process rather than model training and testing.

The results reveal a clear trade-off landscape. RFECV and BorutaSHAP achieve high predictive performance but incur substantial computational overhead, with RFECV in particular requiring more than $14\times$ the CPU effort of SHAPRefine. At the other extreme, MI is computationally light but consistently underperforms on predictive metrics, reflecting its inability to capture nonlinear dependencies in complex network traffic. PowerSHAP, while efficient and producing the smallest subset,

TABLE V: Performance comparison of feature selection methods using XGBoost on the 5GNIDD dataset.

Method	No. of Features	Predictive Performance				Efficiency Performance				
		Acc.	Prec.	Rec.	F1	Time (s)	CPU Effort (%*s)	Average Memory Usage (MB)	Energy Consumed (mWh)	
Mutual Information	11	93.07	95.04	94.96	95	236.49	988.37	2805.07	995.54	
RFECV	30	98.49	99.09	98.74	98.9	1045.14	21662.54	2459.62	5661.69	
BorutaSHAP	29	98.49	99.09	98.74	98.9	203.79	17212.60	3713.43	2575.55	
PowerSHAP	10	98.46	99.07	98.72	98.88	296.12	27361.62	2632.87	4107.82	
SHAPRefine	11	98.68	99.19	98.91	99.04	72.78	6886.82	2983.32	999.52	

sacrifices both accuracy and stability, illustrating the risk of overly aggressive elimination.

SHAPRefine balances this spectrum by combining competitive predictive performance with low computational footprint. Its selection process keeps time, CPU effort, and energy consumption significantly lower than other XAI-based wrappers, while avoiding the accuracy losses of simpler filters. Compared with training directly on the full feature set, SHAPRefine introduces a modest initial selection overhead, but Fig. 2 shows that these costs are quickly offset: cumulative inference time grows far more slowly as the scale of data and the number of inference instances increase, making the benefits more pronounced at deployment scale. Overall, these findings demonstrate that SHAPRefine not only maintains state-of-the-art accuracy but also delivers sustainable efficiency improvements, ensuring that feature selection strengthens rather than burdens IDS performance in operational B5G environments.

Fig. 2: Cumulative inference time across deployment rounds for XGBoost models trained with and without SHAPRefine on the 5GNIDD dataset.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented SHAPRefine, a novel, model-agnostic feature selection framework that leverages class-wise SHAP aggregation to improve both predictive accuracy and computational efficiency in IDS. The principles of SHAPRefine extend naturally to other high-dimensional tabular learning tasks beyond security, suggesting opportunities for cross-domain applications. Experiments across multiple classifiers and diverse IDS datasets, including modern 5G traffic, showed that SHAPRefine consistently enhances detection performance—particularly for minority-class attacks—while reducing feature dimensionality by over 90% and lowering training cost and energy usage by up to 95%. These results highlight SHAPRefine as the first XAI-driven framework to move beyond post-hoc interpretability and enable automated, class-aware refinement for IDS. Future work will explore accelerating the selection phase through parallelization and evaluating SHAPRefine in O-RAN environments, including

its integration into lightweight security xApps for practical deployment.

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